

Rishiraj Biofield Effect

Human "bio-field" can continue after death as ghost.

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Abstract:

A unique property of the human "bio-field" has been discovered during examining several videos on different websites where people have uploaded videos showing some mysterious events. These videos are showing ghost-like shadows following the walking persons. Some videos are showing human-like shadow images walking alone. There are videos showing ghost-like images coming out from closed doors. In the absence of any scientific answer to such mysterious recordings people are found to believe them as images of ghosts or the results of some glitches in the cameras. The owners of such videos are mostly telling that their videos have captured images of real ghosts. Some video owners have left it to the people to decide and comment.

A minute study of some videos was done to find out any logical truth. It was found that these videos are showing some unknown property of human "bio-field". It is a new discovery of science that will help us understand many mysterious paranormal events based on scientific principles. It is discovered that these ghost images are formed by human bio-fields.

Fair dealing of copyrighted contents:

This paper is based on observations displaced by other people who themselves are not clear about their observations. They have mostly left it for the public to decide about their unexpected mysterious video and still photo recordings.

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Introduction:

The contents are from a small book namely "RISHIRAJ BIOFIELD EFFECT" written by the author of this paper. The book is copyrighted in India on 25/06/2024.

A new discovery will assist us to correct some flaws of present day knowledge of science. Many non-scientific perceptions will become easy to understand. In the absence of the availability of ultimate scientific truth about paranormal events, hypnotizes, black magic and ghost sightings etc large population is confused, did not know what to do, following some rituals blindly, harming others for their own benefit.

As the discovery of a new kind of radiation cannot be fully presented in the print format, a movie file is created to demonstrate real observations. The following video will be helpful to understand the further explanations:

<https://youtu.be/EVoKiSAjS0M>

Main Text:

Centuries of physics research have found nothing like ghosts, which is why physicists say they can't exist. Now some video recordings are available to explain the observation of ghosts as a scientific event.

The primary operational system of the brain involves the electrical branch of science. The metabolism is a precisely chained oxide reduction process and electromagnetic fields get generated during the biochemical process. These fields are named "bio-field".

The cloud of charged bio electromagnetic field, resembling its structural area with a complete photographic image of a person, has been seen following walking persons.

Some clips are shown here:

There are several videos available on different websites where people are showing videos which were unknowingly captured by cameras. These videos are showing ghost like identities following the walking persons, showing human shadow like identities crossing the roads without getting disturbed by moving vehicles, human shadow like identities going in or out of closed doors and images of the persons not matching with their images seen through mirrors.

For example, the mystery of a video of the following clip is still baffling every one. There is a general tendency to call such videos fake and edited.

People are also asking how come in the last 20 years since camera enabled mobile phones not one ghost sighting has ever been recorded. Why are the so-called sightings of ghosts, aliens and demons still captured on murky and dimly lit recordings?

The answer to this question can be like this...

The rays coming from the bio-field are not exactly similar to light rays. These rays mostly in its concentrated form require more time to create any reaction on our retina or the camera recording system. In case of HD cameras, time of window opening to receive light is reduced by increasing FPS (Frame Rate per Second). For radiation coming from bio-field, it is not the Frame Rate per Second that matters; it requires sufficient frame time to have an effect which is mostly available with old generation cameras.

Here such mysterious events will be explained scientifically based on a new discovery.

A clip from a video is showing a human-like shadow coming out from a closed door of a lift and moving towards the stairs.

A shadow almost matching the shape of the walking person is seen following the person. Most people have assumed that some ghost is walking behind this person.

Ref Source: <https://avtosfer.az/az/maraqli/cinler-kameraya-dusdu-video-52481>

Ref Source: https://youtu.be/WVTRQCiTxls?si=Zj5qKt8ywS_1Yb34

24th Oct 2024

It is being shown by the title “Huge Ghost Following a Boy on the Road”

Shown by the title “Real Ghost running behind a Man Caught on Tape’

This clip is from a video that was recorded by a dashboard camera.

As the person driving the car found it unnatural, he uploaded the video at youtube.com for the public to comment.

It can be seen that the light shadow is walking by her side.

Ref Source: <https://youtu.be/k9I5z12RzQo?si=rTkmGj-jEBHP9fs7>

A shadow image suddenly appears behind a walking lady and starts chasing her.

Shadows resembling walking persons are found to be crossing the road. These shadows are not disturbed by moving vehicles. Vehicles are seen running through the walking shadows.

This video was also available on youtube.com. A dark shadow of some human was seen chasing a person. Most people have assumed that some ghost is chasing the person.

Ref Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=83DSip6vCHM>

This ghost puzzle is being explained by a new discovery of an unknown property of “bio-field”. The charged bio electromagnetic field “bio-field” releases waves of some mysterious energy that can also produce photoelectric effect.

There can be two options for the “bio-field” to release image copy of the person to get recorded by the camera:

1. The “bio-field” has got detached from the walking person and is moving behind the person.
2. The “bio-field” while maintaining original overlapping position with the person is releasing energy waves with slower speed than light rays.

It can be seen that the outline of the shadow is matching with the position of the person when he was at the location of its previous shadow. This proves that his “bio-field” has released energy waves during his position at the location of chasing shadow. As the energy waves from “bio-field” are traveling with slower speed than light rays, by the time the image of the shadow reaches the camera, the person has moved a little forward, and his real image, traveling with speed of light, also reaches the camera at the same time.

The shadow is matching with his image when he was at the location of the shadow

Here too it is an image of his bio-field reaching the camera at slower speed than light rays.

Here again, a simple comparison of some frames of the video is showing that the shadow is emerging from the walking person. It is discovered that some unknown rays (Rishi rays) are coming from the walking person. These mysterious Rishi rays are traveling slower than light rays but are having photoelectric properties of light as these Rishi rays are also being recorded by the camera. It can be seen that when the person has moved forward in the next frame, a shadow of his previous position reaches the camera with some delay.

Now look again at this clip showing a lady crossing the road.

This video is recorded by a road side CCTV camera.

A woman is seen traveling on the other side of the road.

It is a busy traffic road.

The woman is looking left before she can cross the road.

The woman has started crossing the road

Now she has started walking fast.

As she was almost running, a black shadow image started appearing behind her.

The dark human-like image appears to be chasing her.

It can be seen that the dark image is almost a photocopy of her image when she was at the location of the dark image.

This video is again showing that the shadow is emerging from the walking person itself. It again confirms that some unknown rays are coming out from the walking person. These mysterious Rishi rays are traveling slower than light but are having photoelectric properties of light as these Rishi rays are also being recorded by the camera. It can be seen that when the person has moved forward in the next frame, a shadow of his previous position reaches the camera with some delayed time which is equivalent to the time taken by the person to move from the position of shadow to the position at which the camera recorded the real image.

Even when she was out of the camera view area, her shadow image was being recorded by the camera. Several such types of video recordings are available where only shadows are found to be walking alone.

Such walking alone mysterious shadows of the persons get recorded by the camera when the person has already gone far away from the camera. As such shadows do not represent any real identity of the object located at its visible position, it is a virtual image formed by Rishi rays that have already left its visible location. The shadow image will not get disturbed by any traffic moving through it or by strong wind as nothing associated with it is present at its visible location. As the Rishi rays forming the shadow image at the camera have already left its emerging location, the shadow by some people is being considered as some visible ghost.

In the next clip from a video a similar incident is noticed. A shadow of a person is crossing the road. But in this case too the shadow is undisturbed by the moving vehicles. There is a strong possibility based on the previous clip of a woman crossing the road that it is also a virtual shadow image formed by a person who has just crossed the road a few minutes earlier.

Ref Source: <https://twitter.com/TheSun/status/1238454765928890369>

Ref Source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cOfoRRt_IbU

Her shadow is seen descending the escalator exactly the way she was descending while the man in white dress was also descending the escalator.

It appears as if some ghost-like identity is accompanying the man in white dress.

It is not any ghost but a delayed image of the woman formed by slow moving Rishi rays. The Bio-Field during some unique body conditions of the person starts transmitting concentrated forms of newly discovered Rishi rays.

Rishi rays are seen traveling with a speed of about 1.40 meters per second as compared to the speed of sound with an average speed of 340 meters per second. As compared to light rays, the Rishi rays are seen traveling with exceptionally slow speed.

Reflection of the woman is seen 2nd time while she has walked before the mirror only once.

See the mirror at the top left corner. The repetition of the image reflection is due to slow moving Rishi rays. The human bio-field can release extremely slow moving radiations under some unique conditions. These newly discovered radiations (Rishi rays) have a property resembling the light rays. When a person is releasing Rishi rays, the natural light coming after reflection from the human body and the Rishi rays emerging from the bio-field are traveling the same path but with variable velocities. As the Rishi rays are traveling slower than light, its reflection from the mirror is creating a delayed 2nd image of the person.

The shadow image from the “bio-field” is not moving on the exact path of the lady’s walking path. This suggests that the mysterious energy rays are not moving in a straight line. These rays are likely to be traveling on a curved path while moving similar to spiral winds.

Here path of the shadow is shown with red arrow and the path of the lady is shown with yellow arrow. The shadow is not moving on the exact path of the lady's walking path. This suggests that the mysterious energy rays are not moving in a straight line.

These rays are likely to be travelling on a curved path while moving similar to spiral winds. This can be one of the reasons of shadow taking a little drifted position. In case the rays of shadow image are moving in a curved path, the rays after moving a complete circular path can reach the same location again and get recorded by the camera while the person had moved quite far away from the camera field.

This clip is from a video where two security guards are trying to locate a person that was not visible to them. They were instructed to look out for the person by a security person from the guard room that was able to see the stranger on the CCTV camera screen.

As per Rishiraj biofield effect, black shadow image is a virtual image of some person who was present here during some previous time.

All such videos need to be examined for previous time to find out if some person resembling the shadow image was actually present at the nearby location.

Some human identity is seen on CCTV monitor but not visible to the guards

For the last many years people are not able to find the answer as to why the security guards are not able to locate a person who was visible on CCTV screen but was not visible to them. The CCTV screen was showing the security guards moving through the dark human-like figure while moving their torch in every direction. When they could not locate the stranger, the security guard who was seeing the stranger on CCTV screen too rushed to the location where he was seeing the stranger. He too was not able to find the stranger.

Now, based on Rishi Raj's bio field effect, the mystery is resolved. It has been explained that Rishi rays which get released from human bio fields are traveling with variable speeds on curved paths similar to whirlwinds. Similar to wind that moves in a spinning or swirling motion, the photons of light rays or any kind of moving energy, including sound waves, can also acquire swirling motion.

A possible scientific explanation is explained in this diagram.

The real person was standing in the past at some nearby location.

He was releasing Rishi rays from his bio field.

The Rishi rays were swirling at a very slow speed.

When the Rishi rays were traveling a distance from point A to point B, the image of the stranger was getting recorded on CCTV.

The image of the stranger appeared to be coming from point C.

During the time of Rishi rays being observed from point A to point B on CCTV camera screen, images of the guards were also reaching the CCTV from point X to point Y.

The mystery of two headed deer is finally explained by Rishiraj Biofield Effect

Ref Source: https://www.youtube.com/shorts/ZZJm7G_AN2c

A TITOK user has posted this video showing a deer with another head for about 10 seconds. A Strange Spotting youtube channel owner tried to explain the event by suggesting that a second deer is also peeking from behind the tree. His explanation is shown at the following Link:

Ref Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uRgA1roESJk>

As per his perception, the two deer got positioned one behind the other that tricked the human mind to believe seeing a single deer with two heads.

The following clips showing step by step movement of two heads is contradicting his perception of two deer.

See Frame-1, 2, 3: Splitting of left ear from one image to two images. It can be seen that the image of head-2 is coming out of head-1. The 2nd head tagged with blue pointer is clearly appearing from behind the head tagged with red line.

Frame- 1 to 6: head-1 of real deer is moving towards left while head-2 has turned to right.

See Frame- 7 to 9: The head-1 and head-2 are moving down.

See Frame-10: The head-2 have merged with the original head-1

See frame- 11: The real deer is walking away.

Here it can be seen that the possibility of another deer coming from behind the tree and placing its head-2 exactly behind the head-1 without being recorded is not possible.

See frame- 11: When the deer is walking away, some part of the 2nd deer should have been recorded. The person who has recorded this event must be watching the scene for some more time even after recording the event. How the 2nd deer disappeared behind the tree without any of its any part getting recorded.

Well, in the absence of any other scientific explanation, people are bound to support two deer concepts.

Now with the discovery of a new Rishiraj biofield effect, this event can be explained as another unique example based on several recordings of chasing shadows.

As per the Rishiraj biofield effect, some Rishi rays are emerging from “bio-field”. These newly discovered wave energy is mostly traveling slower than light rays. For some unique instances the Rishi rays are also found to be traveling faster than light rays. These Rishi rays are mostly getting produced or becoming concentrated enough to be noticed, very rarely, from the over developed or over heated or over charged “bio-field” of humans and living creatures.

Based on some real recordings by the video cameras, it has been explained earlier that the “bio-field” are generating photocopy type images after some delayed time as compared to the real image. The real image from the actual object and a shadow image from its previous position, traveling with some slow speed, get recorded simultaneously. For this reason, duplicate images get recorded by the camera. The second image from the “bio-field” is found to be semi transparent or dark black or almost similar to the original image. The transparency factor is due to the fact that when Rishi rays from the shadow image begin traveling towards the camera lens, faster moving rays of the real background also reach the lens at the same time.

The mystery of double head deer can be better explained by the Rishiraj bio-field effect. In the image of double head deer shown below, the possible movement of head by the deer just before the camera recording is explained. The deer has moved his head from “1” to “3” and back to “5”. When the head was moving from “4” to “5”, the camera recorded a real image but at the same time the camera could also capture a delayed image from the “bio-field” when the head was moving from point “2” to point “3”.

Rishi rays are also found to be traveling faster than light.

The faster moving Rishi rays have been noticed by studying the following video.

The video is still available at the following link:

Ref Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pbTf37p-H8Q>

This scene begins after 4 minutes.

A shadow image is seen moving before a walking person. Until now we have seen shadows following the people from behind. It was explained that Rishi rays from the bio-field are travelling with velocities slower than light rays. Some successive clips from the video are shown here to explain the pattern of the shadow with respect to the walking person.

In this clip, the shadow visible at point “2” is matching with the position of the person when he moves to location “1”. The lower frame of the clip shows the position of the person that will be at point “1”.

When he reaches the location “1”, the shadow image is seen walking further and is not matching with his adjoining real image. The position of the legs from his image is not matching with the position of legs of the shadow, but it is matching with the position of legs of the shadow visible at upper frame.

For his next steps again, the shadow at point “2” is matching with the position of the person when he moves to location “1”. The shadow of his feet at the location “2” is not matching with the position of the feet of his adjoining image. His right foot is above the ground whereas the shadow is showing right foot touching the ground and left foot just above the ground.

When he reached the location “1”, his corresponding shadow was already visible at “2” during his previous position.

Shadow of his feet visible at the upper part of the clip is matching with his real image at the lower part of the clip.

For his next steps, the same explanation is true.

For every frame during his crossing the road, the explanation given is repeated.

As per Physics, it is a well known concept that nothing has been found to be moving faster than light and nothing can overtake the velocity of light or any other electromagnetic waves. However, some vibrations from the “bio-field” are seen traveling faster than light. The shadow getting recorded in advance of the image of an object that has not yet reached the location of the image can only be possible when Rishi rays coming from the shadow are reaching faster than the light rays coming from the image. As per earlier such events, the Rishi rays from “bio-field” are also found to be moving a little slower than light.

For slower Rishi rays from the “bio-field”, the shadow is seen chasing the walking person. For the Rishi rays traveling faster than the light rays, the shadow image will be moving ahead of the person.

What are the chances of this video being faked?

This video appears to be recorded by a CCTV camera installed at the road side.

In case some video editing is used to create this fake video, no one will try an extremely difficult act to implant future shadow images of a walking person when it will be more convenient to copy and paste his simultaneous images as other shadow images from the same video frame. Generally the purpose of making the fake videos is to get more viewers, and implanting the simultaneous shadows from the same video frame serves that purpose without using extremely difficult video manipulation tasks. As the person responsible for this video was not aware that some person will use a new discovery to analyze this video, he would never have imagined creating a very complex fake video to justify the new findings.

The “bio-field” is not the waste by-product. It is a very important product required to maintain operational functions of our body.

Our conscious system which interacts with our surroundings by the use of our sensory organs is communicating with our self (our real identity independent of our physical body) by inducing vibrations in our Bio-field. And our self having its presence mostly in our Bio-field and our body is operating our physical body, by the use of some electromagnetic energy of our Bio-field. Our self is controlling contraction or relaxation of the muscles of our body, managing replacement of old cells by new cells and keeping fulfilling its desires. Our body’s primary function is achieved by our bones and muscles. Without the bones and muscles our body will be similar to the contents of an egg. Our skin is not the external last layer of our body. The boundary that contains our bio-field is the real outer limit of our body. The present understanding of the brain is that it is a complex organ that controls thought, memory, emotion, touch, motor skills, vision, breathing, temperature, hunger and every process that regulates our body. It is assumed that Neurons of the brain communicate with each other by sending chemicals, called neurotransmitters, across a tiny space called a synapse, between the axons and dendrites of nearby neurons. We call the brain a complex organ as we don’t know its complete functions. For some very strange incidents related to the brain we are not sure how such developments are possible.

It has been observed that after removing one half of the brain, a procedure performed to treat neurological disorders like epilepsy, it causes the remaining parts to gradually form strong nerve connections within the existing hemisphere. It is said this rewiring potentially helps the body to function as if the brain was intact.

Some blind people are able to "see" out of their ears.

Ref Source: <https://www.insider.com/facts-about-the-brain-2018-12#some-blind-people-are-able-to-see-out-of-their-ears-10>

According to a study by the University of Montreal, the brain can actually rewire itself in some pretty cool ways.

When researchers looked at the brain activity of people who had been born blind, they found that the part of the brain that's usually responsible for vision can shift gears to process sound information.

This means that blind people may "see" sounds in the same part of their brain that sighted people use to tackle visual information.

Scientists have found that specific areas of the brain have distinct connections with different parts of the body, and each part of our body is controlled by the corresponding area of the brain. But if some part of the body is removed, the corresponding part of the brain never gets switched off or continues to remain waiting to operate the missing part of the body. The jobless part of the brain, which is still getting energy for its operation, shifts its gear to strengthen the operation of another part of the body. It is not working like a computer which will not resume working till the defective part is replaced.

The main question is that which part of the brain is managing such entirely new construction and repairing activities?

It will be more appropriate for any construction and repairing section of our body to have its presence in our Bio-field.

Our self, that we recognize as “me, my” is in possession of all our conscious resources and memory storage. We are not keeping these valuable resources tied to any biological cells that have a very short life span. The scientists have a perception that our memory is stored at some physical location within our skull and in packets tied to the biological material. In case our memory is located in some biological cells, there should be some temporary storage to hold the memory during replacement of the old cell by the new cell. Why not the temporary storage, that can hold the memory during replacement of cells, can keep the memory permanently? In case the bio-field is acting like a bridge to move the memory from a dying cell to the newborn cell, it can keep the memory in its own area like the RAM of a computer. The computer has two types of memory namely RAM and disc type storage. If we create a computer that will keep operational throughout its life span and provide it with exceptionally large RAM, we can discard the use of hard disc

type storage. In case our bio-field is serving a purpose similar to the RAM of computers, nature will not require any other wasteful technology to keep our memory in unstable biological cells. If this comes out to be true, our bio-field will be found to be complete “we” but without our physical hard body.

In the near future, scientific evidence will be available to explain that the cloud of charged bio electromagnetic field, having its area and resemblance with our latest photographic image, can retain its identity after the physical body vanishes. Yes, if the smoke can continue floating in the air after the fire that has generated it is gone, the bio-field too will remain existent after the body is gone. The bio-field occupied area can expand like a very large balloon, large enough to fit a big hall, or can shrink to an area much smaller than a pin tip, and can transform in the shape of the body's latest photographic image.

The body-less wandering bio-field can be found to overpower people with weaker bio-field and the captured person will start displaying dual personality from both the bio-fields. If the bio-field from a body of a person, who was a smoker and of bad character, overtakes a non smoker, the non smoker will also start smoking and become bad character.

The bio-field of a diseased person will create virtual symptoms of the same disease in the captured person. Many sick people are found to get healed within minutes just after the extra external impure bio-field (negative energy) vanishes from their body. The people with their own diseased bio-field are found to get cured from their fatal diseases when they willingly invite healthy and strong bio-field to stay in their body. Some scientific gadgets can be developed to calm down the bio-field of any individual, or ward off attacking bio-field.

Many people have learnt the art to influence and control the bio-field of other people. Millions of people are approaching them and spending a lot of time and money for their relief from their variety of sufferings. In the absence of availability of ultimate scientific truth, large population of the world is confused, did not know what to do, following some rituals blindly, harming others for their own benefit, performing some wrong and painful yoga meditations by staying alone at higher peaks of frozen Himalayas, performing sacrifices of animals and humans, using human skulls as their eating bowl, and many more strange acts.

Sir Albert Einstein has stated that Photons are energy packets that show both wave-like and particle nature. They have no mass but have high energy. They move at the speed of light. Their energy level is determined by the frequency of the electromagnetic radiation waves.

What is a Photon? Photons are explained as energy packets emerging from any source. They are defined as packets of energy emitted from a source in the form of electromagnetic radiation. Sir Albert Einstein proposed and explained these particles in the year 1905. It was his theory of photoelectric effect that properly described the existence and emission of photons of light.

The scientists believe that the photons, moving along the light rays, are the main energy packets responsible for creating images by different kinds of cameras. Scientists believe that we too can see an image when photons from light strike our retina. We have also learnt that the energy packets, known as photons, can move only with the speed of light as light ray is their transporting medium.

There is evidence to believe that images can also get recorded from rays not traveling with the speed of light. How can some energy that is not traveling with the speed of light can carry photons and create images on camera?

This suggests that either the photons will not always travel along with the light rays or there are some other kinds of energy packets moving with variable speeds that can work similar to photons energy. Nature never uses two different options simultaneously to accomplish any task. Nature will always choose only the best at a time.

If the photons are not the only energy packets that can create photoelectric or photographic effects, the mechanism of seeing images by the eyes is not necessarily what scientists are describing. The bio-field will be found to be more involved in the process of seeing the images and storing the image data in its RAM type memory.

The researchers have tried to explain the Visual Pathway that we use to store and view the image created by our eyes. The Visual Pathway is assumed to be like fine electric cables meant to carry electricity

signals. Can electric current flow through veins placed in highly wet areas that are carrying some fluids and are not insulated to protect leakage of current?

In case of photoelectric cells, the production of electricity stops as soon as the light stops striking the photosensitive cells. But in the case of the eye retina, the impact of striking light rays remains effective for about 5 seconds after the light stops reaching the retina. Not only that, the processing system of the retina starts creating the reverse of the image received (negative of the image). And the negative effect fades away in about 5 seconds. Such activity suggests that unique flexibility behaviour of the retina screen is playing a more important role.

The retina is much like our external skin but is extremely fine and sensitive so that a slightest pressure from the striking light rays pushes its affected surface area exactly similar to our outer skin during any pressure on it. Once pressure is stopped, the retina's affected surface tries to move back to its normal state but during this process its surface, due to momentum, goes to the other side of its normal position. It takes some time for the retina surface to come to its normal state. This can be the main reason to visualise some residual negative of an image during the time the retina's specific area is in the opposite location.

Some images seen suggest some residual effect remains on the retina for about 5 seconds after the image source is removed. This is the most unique and not yet explained by the support of known scientific principles. These are being termed as optical illusions affecting visual perception. An illusion is something that isn't real. It may look real, but it's actually imagination or like hallucination. All the illusions, paranormal activities, magic, ghost sightings etc are due to our underdeveloped scientific knowledge.

For example the following is not an optical illusion but it suggests that our understanding of the functioning of retina and visual pathway is faulty.

Ref Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=m4nzqmqj52kA>

If we continue seeing the red dot for about 30 seconds and then start looking towards white area, a positive image of the scene starts appearing before our eyes. This type of residual effect vanishes within 5 seconds.

Similarly, a negative effect can be viewed for any positive image. Why this type of negative effect is felt has a scientific reasoning. Can't there be some other mechanism for the retina to sense the striking light rays?

Whatever is being viewed by our self is the actual activity happening on the retina screen and not due to any unscientific hallucination act. Our retina surface is not only affected by striking light rays but its every minute surface is also kept adjusted physically by our conscious self to receive only meaningful images.

During viewing any scene, our retina surface is creating different wave-like patterns on its surface like ripples of water surface. This can be the main reason for seeing the moving effect for a period of 5 seconds in a stationary image after an image with moving contents is watched for a period of about 30 seconds.

In the act of hypnotizing too the role of bio-field will be found to be the main player. The bio-field of the hypnotizer can be found to be expanding like a balloon to cover persons willing to get hypnotized. All the persons who have willingly got disconnected from their respective bio-field start obeying instructions from the hypnotizer's bio-field.

Not only that, the hypnotizer can also transfer memory contents from the bio-field of the hypnotized persons to its own bio-field.

Contrary to the working principle of photoelectric cells, the image seen by us is required to remain stationary on the retina surface for some minimum time so that the retina cells are able to sense the striking light rays. Some experts will say that the human eye can see between 30 and 60 frames per second. That is the image needs to remain stationary on the retina for $1/30$ seconds to $1/60$ seconds for different groups of people. In the case of a person that requires $1/30$ seconds to complete the process of recognition of image, there are likely to be different series of processing steps within the period of $1/30$ seconds that are required to build some complete packet of image information that can reach to our next sensing stage. Most DSLR and mirror less cameras can shoot as fast as $1/4000$ of a second using the mechanical shutter. Some of the more advanced cameras can shoot as fast as $1/8000$ of a second with mechanical shutters, and even faster when using electronic shutters. That clearly suggests that the process of image getting recorded by human organs and man made cameras must not be similar and same.

Why are the Cones and Rods of our eyes placed in the opposite direction of the striking light rays is still a mystery.

In physics, the photoelectric cells are always placed facing incoming light rays. Does that not suggest that Cones and Rods are not working on the principle of photoelectric cells but are designed to sense variable pressures on the hard side of the retina screen? All our sensory systems are designed to detect variable pressure changes and not any electromagnetic energy variations. Our skin, muscles and connective tissue too have mechanoreceptors to detect variation of pressure, deformation and strain.

To carry on the detection system, the surface area of the receiving signals is kept wet and flexible by different types of unique hormone fluids. Constant development and supply of these consumable hormone fluids is maintained by the larger portion of our brain area. Since many of these consumable hormone fluids

have a very short life span the sensory organs required to utilize them are kept nearest to their production area. The design of our face is not an artistic act but is based on scientific necessities.

It has been observed that the many body parts remain active and alive for a certain time period after they are removed from the main body.

For example, it was observed that a lizard's tail keeps moving roughly for one minute after it came off from the lizard. The tail is showing wriggling around on the floor as though it has a mind of its own. The creepy spasms continue for about sixteen seconds.

Ref Source: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i6pcNRkqsZs>

See event No 27 (Display time: 3:55 to 4:52)

Why did it continue moving for about sixteen seconds after its connecting nerves were not able to communicate with its mind? Why could it not continue moving for a much longer time?

Some patients are found to experience a variety of vivid sensations from the missing limb. Does the present knowledge of science have any answer?

These observations are giving a hint that our brain is not controlling the movement of our mussels and body parts. Our brain is only working on the principle of other glands that are producing specific types of chemical fluids. These different varieties of chemical fluids are much like our different grades of petrol meant for cars, trucks and airplanes. Some variety of our chemical fluid keeps burning to generate heat and electromagnetic radiations. Other varieties burn to generate electromagnetic radiation on getting pressed. All such electromagnetic radiations are meant to create electronic ripples in our Bio-field.

As the Bio-field can reach the separated lizard tail, it tries to manage its survival. But, once the stock of chemical fluid (specific type of hormone) in the lizard tail burns up and its supply chain is already broken, the Bio-field loses its communication and control with a separated lizard tail. It also suggests that cones and rods of our eyes, sensors of our skin, chemo sensors of nasal cavity, and taste buds of our tongue are the chambers to store specific types of chemical fluids meant to get burned up during a specific range of vibrating pressures.

The network of veins of the brain area is mostly designed to maintain coordinated movement of eyeballs, neck and all other muscles during hearing of any sound or getting signals from our bio-field. The white matter of the brain is mostly producing consumable hormone fluids for the use of the sensory organs. And the best location of our memory is our bio-field.

Our brain matter is functioning like a complex gland similar to many other smaller glands of our body.

In case our memory is residing in our bio-field, our bio-field is complete “we” without our physical body. The human soul can be an identity of bio-field.

A CCTV recording is showing a human shadow-like image standing near the wreckage just after the accident. This shadow image is similar to the chasing shadows shown earlier. People consider it the soul of the dead person. The souls are actually the detached bio-field of the dead person.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LYgqbFIS3JA>

This photo was taken in 1984 of a car crash where a boy died. The picture was taken by a police officer. The first one is his body in the car and the second is showing an image of his face. Some believe it to be his spirit. Scientifically, we can believe it to be his detached bio-field.

From a CCTV recording in a hospital, a bio-field image of a person is seen getting detached from his body just after his heart beat stops. Paranormal supporters believe that a soul is leaving the body.

<https://youtu.be/20k-A3N1SI8>

Conclusion

1. The human “bio-field” is not a waste by-product. It is a very important product required to maintain operational functions of our body. The cloud of charged bio electromagnetic field, namely “bio-field”, covering its area with our complete photographic image, including our clothing, is found to create its coloured image exactly similar to our visible physical structure.
2. The “bio-field” is the area that keeps our emotional parameters like ego, anger, depression, happiness, fear, shyness, cravings and many more that we can not mimic by our scientific gadgets. The ego is the very primal power that holds together the identity we call, “me” and without the activities of these emotional parameters our physical body will remain non responsive, like a patient in coma. It is complete “WE” along with our memory without our physical body.
3. A unique property of “bio-field” has been discovered. Its radiating energy, during some unique conditions, can create a photoelectric effect but it is not traveling with the speed of light, rather it is found to be moving with extremely variable speeds, many a times on curved path, even faster than speed of light.
4. During the motion of a person, the cameras while recording images of the person can also show its duplicate image formed by the “bio-field” as a different identity. The duplicate image is formed due to its slower or faster radiations from the speed of light.
5. Cones and Rods of our eyes are placed in the opposite direction of the striking light rays. In physics, the photoelectric cells are always placed facing incoming light rays. It suggests that Cones and Rods are not working on the principle of photoelectric cells.
6. The retina is much like our external skin and is covered with an extremely fine and sensitive lubricant layer forming the most delicate skin like structure. The pressure from the striking light rays pushes the retina’s surface area similar to our outer skin during any pressure on it. The retina’s most sensitive layer is made to vibrate with the frequency of striking light wave frequency. The vibrating layer of the retina is able to transfer the pattern of vibrations in the area of the “bio-field”.
7. All our sensory systems are designed to detect variable mechanical vibrations and not any electromagnetic energy variations. All vibration patterns from different sensory organs remain present in our “bio-field” area in the form of similar vibrations on a common timeline. The timeline not only tags vibrating patterns from the sensory systems but also includes all emotional parameters.
8. In the act of hypnotizing too the role of bio-field will be found to be the main player. The bio-field of the hypnotizer can be found to be expanding like a balloon to cover persons willing to get hypnotized. All the persons who have willingly got disconnected from their respective bio-field can start obeying instructions from the hypnotizer’s bio-field.
9. Our brain is not controlling the movement of our muscles and body parts. Our bio-field is using layers of our brain as a switch board to operate body parts.
10. The network of veins and nerve cells of the brain area is mostly designed to maintain coordinated movement of eyeballs, neck and all other muscles during hearing of any sound or getting signals from our bio-field.
11. The area of the brain is mostly producing consumable hormone fluids for the use of the sensory organs. Since many of these consumable hormone fluids have a very short life span the sensory organs required to utilize them are kept nearest to their production area.
12. Our self, that we recognize as “me, my” is in possession of all our conscious resources and memory storage. We are not keeping these valuable resources tied to any biological cells that have a very short life span, but in the bio-field in the form of different vibrating patterns.
13. The “bio-field” can keep its identity even after the physical body vanishes. The wandering “bio-field” of the dead keeps interfering with the “bio-field” of weaker individuals. People with any extra “bio-field” will start showing components/symptoms of external “bio-field” as dual personality.

